

**Developing Gender-Awareness and Inclusivity in Teaching and
Research in Business and Management Schools**

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Abstract:

Gender inequality patterns in Business and Management (B&M) Schools show little signs of diminishing and, in some cases, have been increasing (Fotaki, 2013; Śliwa et al., 2022). Academics in B&M Schools from a wide range of disciplines with different epistemological and ontological perspectives and research approaches in knowledge production have also increased the complexity of advancing gender equality in B&M Schools. While B&M Schools are responsible for shaping equal and inclusive cultures in organisations as they are at the forefront of fostering prospective business and organisational managers, leaders, and entrepreneurs and influencing research agendas and policy practices. To advance gender equality in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), integrating the gender dimension in research, innovation, and pedagogy are important building blocks in gender equality planning (European Commission, 2021). This PDW will build on exploring and exercising two bespoke guides developed by the Lancaster University Management School's (LUMS) TARGETED-MPI Project team: *The Guide to Developing a Gender-Aware and Inclusive Curriculum* (GIC) and *The Guide to Developing Gender-Aware and Inclusive Research* (GIR). It will also reflect the team's experiences, as a case study, of moving forward with the agenda to integrate the gender dimension into teaching and research. These discussions, knowledge exchange, and exercises will pave the way for starting more open conversations and inform actionable plans for developing gender-awareness and inclusivity in teaching and research to advance equality, diversity, and inclusion in different organisational contexts.

Overview:***Why Business and Management Schools?***

With consortium partners from Europe and the Middle East, the EU Horizon 2020 project, Transparent And Resilient Gender Equality Through Integrated Monitoring Planning and Implementation (TARGETED-MPI), focuses specifically on institutional changes through the development and effective implementation of Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) in Business and Management (B&M) Schools to drive more inclusive, sustainable and transparent academic cultures. There is a wide range of challenges B&M Schools face broadly in advancing gender equality, including career development for academics from different disciplines, a lack of women in professorial roles, and a gender-neutral stance to curriculum development, and research. There has been consistent advocacy for gender-aware and inclusive curricula in B&M Schools. Business and Management education has been critiqued for its persistence in being gender-blind (Forman-Rabinovici and Mandel, 2023), gender-neutral (Howard et al., 2017) or gender-biased

(Peterson, 1993), which typically overlooks the gender perspective. Reflecting these “neutral” standpoints is critical in knowledge reproduction and delivery, which could unravel the underpinned bias, stereotypes, and gendered culture that are unconsciously shaped in teaching and research practices. This has real-world implications as research findings are generalised for entire populations without adequately considering gender differences, thus perpetuating inequality as part of its impact. Thus, it is crucial for B&M Schools to investigate the gendered power relations inherent in research teams, the division of labour, and the way research is conducted. In addition, funding bodies, such as European funding and British Council funding, mandate explicit consideration of gender in research proposals and project developments. Research and innovation within B&M Schools are dedicated to addressing management and business challenges, necessitating inclusive and diverse initiatives to meet contemporary requirements effectively. In sum, gender-aware teaching and research are imperative in B&M Schools.

Building on these crucial needs, the Lancaster University Management School’s (LUMS) TARGETED-MPI team developed two guides, *The Guide to Developing a Gender-Aware and Inclusive Curriculum* (GIC) and *The Guide to Developing Gender-Aware and Inclusive Research* (GIR), as part of the gender equality planning and implementation for the project. The GIC is designed to create gender-aware course content, make gender content more visible and support staff and students’ needs to attend to gender in classroom teaching and assessment. The GIR will provide guidelines for creating gender-aware and inclusive research, applying gender-awareness amongst team members and the research project itself. The development of these two guides draws on academic research, Lancaster University’s Equality, Diversity and Inclusive (EDI) strategy, sister EU projects, and relevant HE reports. Aligning with BAM’s strategic aims of advancing equality, diversity, inclusivity, and respect, the discussions³ and application of these two guides in this PDW will enhance the understanding of the importance of practising gender awareness and inclusivity in pedagogical and research development, which is contextual to different organisations among participants.

Why use LUMS’s guides to develop gender awareness and inclusivity in teaching and research?

A wide range of gender equality projects and organisations have developed general guidelines for gender-aware teaching and research. LUMS project team drew on the resources from these projects and, in particular, reflected on our organisational context and the nature of B&M Schools to integrate a gender dimension into pedagogical development and research. From initiating conversations with key stakeholders, developing and finalising these bespoke guides, and engaging faculty-wide and university-wide networks to incorporate these guides in action planning, the LUMS project team has experienced several challenges and has also been supported by various enablers. Our experience of addressing these challenges and implementing and monitoring these actions towards advancing gender equality will be an insightful case study for colleagues from different Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), and B&M Schools in particular, to reflect and develop gender-aware and inclusive curriculum and research in their institutional contexts.

These two guides and this PDW do not intend to provide a one-off or ‘one size fits all’ solution to address the challenges above. It is hoped, however, that the guides will provide a starting point, which participants can explore, reflect and apply, individually and collaboratively, a wide range of practical and sustainable steps that can be taken forward in research and teaching practices in their institutions.

As a result, as a long-term objective, these starting conversations and actions could lead to increased research projects and curricula taking the gender dimension into account during their development and delivery. Specifically, this PDW aims to

- Share teaching and research scholarship insights in gender-inclusive teaching and research
- Gain an enhanced understanding of the challenges and actionable plans to incorporate gender dimensions into teaching and research
- Support participants in reflecting on the way gender-awareness and inclusivity are currently demonstrated in their research and teaching practices
- Facilitate the establishment of an (informal) network of academics interested in practising these guides to foster sustainable GE practices in their teaching and research environments.⁴

Why it is important for BAM delegates:

With a focus on the B&M Schools context, this PDW is suitable for BAM members, a great number of whom have been taking substantial teaching and research responsibilities in HEIs. It is understood that in different institutions, each department, programme, and module will vary in its pedagogical approach, content, and mode of delivery. Through this workshop, participants could reflect, develop, and plan their bespoke content, checklists, and strategies to be applied in their faculty, schools, programmes, or research development. BAM delegates who undertake, manage, and supervise substantial teaching, learning, and research activities and senior management members who develop educational and research strategies will benefit from participating in this workshop. Similar to the “How To Series” in BAM Community, this workshop provides an opportunity to explore and co-construct the understanding of the significance, present challenges and sustainable action plan for integrating a gender-aware and inclusive lens in teaching and research practices.

An estimate of the number of attendees: 20- 25 participants, in person

Any specific requirements AV/set-up requirements for in-person PDW

- A computer and a screen to show presentation slides
- It would be great if the room could have several small- or medium-sized -tables (for 4-5 people) and chairs that are easy to move around.

Any specific requirements for an online PDW (e.g. breakout rooms, polling, etc.)

N/A5

The Workshop’s Format

The workshop begins with a presentation about the TARGETED-MPI project and the LUMS project team's experiences in incorporating a gender-inclusive lens in teaching and research in LUMS, with a focus on the enablers, barriers and applied strategies in this process (20 minutes). After this presentation, there will be an interactive discussion with guiding questions about the participants' organisational context and Q&As (10 minutes). Provisionally, these guiding questions for participants to reflect on their institutional context include:

- How has the gender dimension been considered in current teaching content and research developments in your institutions?
- Are there any good practices or actions you or your institutions have tried to make teaching and research more gender-inclusive?
- What are the enablers, and what else could be enablers (e.g., key stakeholders, existing EDI structure and initiatives)?
- What barriers have been or will be to incorporating a gender-inclusive lens in teaching and research?

The second presentation will then follow, covering a comprehensive introduction to the two Guides and how to use the Guides (15 minutes). These guides are open and accessible to everyone attending the PDW on the LUMS website. Hard-copy printouts will also be available for those who require them in the room. After the presentation, participants will be invited to join one of two groups. Group 1 will conduct an exercise using the GIC document, and Group 2 will conduct the same exercise using the GiR document (15 mins). Individuals in Group 1 will reflect on applying GIC to develop one of their existing or new module handbooks. Individuals in Group 2 will reflect on how to apply the document to one of their published papers/chapters, working papers, PhD research/monograph or research proposals/bids. During this 15-minute exercise, participants are invited to answer the following three questions as part of their reflection:

- What do you think about the guides?
- Which parts are most helpful and/or you might find challenging to include in your teaching/research practices?
- Based on the guide(s), what steps would you take forward to make teaching/research more gender-aware and inclusive?

Participants from Groups 1 and 2 will then form smaller groups of 4-5 to reflect on their individual answers to these three questions and try to find themes across their reflections (10 minutes). Each group will have a representative who will share their group's feedback and key discussion points (10 minutes).

The session will wrap up, highlighting the key takeaways from this workshop (5 minutes).⁶

The proposed agenda:

o Welcome and introduction of the agenda and aim of this workshop (5 mins)

- Presentation 1: TARGETED-MPI project and LUMS as a case study (20 mins)
- Q&As and large group discussions based on the guiding questions (10 mins)

- Presentation 2: How to use the Guides (15 mins)
- Individual reflections exercise within Groups 1 and 2: Participants individually exercise the
- application of the chosen guide (GIC or GIR) with guiding questions (15 mins)
- Small-group discussions: Participants exercising the same guide form a group of 4-5 to go through
- their answers, and a representative summarises key points on Flipchart paper (10 mins)
- Feedback: Small group feedback on their key discussion points (10 mins)
- Final reflections, questions and closing remarks (5 mins): How do we take accountability (e.g., any working groups, committee, or task force), monitor and evaluate these existing or proposed actions?

Reference:

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